

TEEN CENTER: HOME FOR STUDENTS AT RISK OF DROPPING OUT

Agnes B. Caberoy, Shella Mie M. Duron, Gene A. Ubpon

Lun Padidu National High School, Sarangani, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13903571>

ABSTRACT

The study proposed the establishment of a School-Based Teen Center that may address not only academic needs but also social, emotional, and mental health challenges by offering tutoring, mentoring, counseling, and extracurricular activities under one roof. The participants were selected through purposive sampling technique from Grade 7 to Grade 10 who were officially enrolled in Lun Padidu National High School for this SY 2023-2024. Document analysis was utilized in the generation of data on the reasons of the participants who are at risk of dropping out. Thematic analysis was used in analyzing the generated data specifically on their responses. The findings revealed that most of the participants have a lack of interest in attending school, experienced health issues, family issues, and distance from home to school. For this, the researchers strongly recommend the school administration to establish the school-based Teen Center. This project will create a comprehensive safety net for students grappling with various issues. Thus, this will complement and reinforce the role of schools, families, and communities in educating, counseling, and empowering adolescents.

Keywords: *teen center, at-risk, issues, academic needs, challenges*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, high school dropout rates continue to be a significant concern in education systems worldwide, with detrimental effects on individual students, communities, and societies at large.

Numerous studies have identified a wide range of factors contributing to dropout among at-risk learners. Academic factors such as low achievement, academic disengagement, and lack of school connectedness have been consistently linked to dropout (Rumberger, 2011). Additionally, socio-economic factors including poverty, parental education level, and family instability significantly influence dropout rates (Dynarski et.al., 2008). Moreover, behavioral issues, mental health challenges, and peer influences contribute to the dropout phenomenon (Jimerson et al., 200).

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) reports a drop of more than five million in the number of enrollees for the school year 2023-2024 from last year. DepEd said there are 22,917,725 enrollees recorded for public and private schools, state universities and colleges, including Philippine schools overseas.

In Lun Padidu National High school, it is continuously experiencing students who are at risk of dropping out. Specifically in the school year 2021-2022, there were 25 or 1.9% out of 1350 students, 20 or 1.4% for school year 2022-2023 and 18 or 1.2% out of 1503 students dropped.

In response to these alarming dropout rates, the Researchers were motivated to conduct a research study for the establishment of teen center to bring to light the at risk dropping out learners in Junior High School. As noted by Adams (2019) that Teen centers often provide counseling services or peer support programs, which help address the mental health needs of students. Adolescence is a critical time for emotional development and having a space where students can seek guidance or talk about their feelings can reduce anxiety, depression, and other mental health issues. Further, Jones (2021) and Roberts et al. (2020) confirmed that teen center offers tutoring, homework help, and other educational programs that can enhance learning outside of the classroom. This additional support is particularly important for students who may struggle academically or lack resources at home. This will help the school to reduce dropout rates and promote academic success.

Research Questions

This study described the reasons of Junior High School learners in Lun Padidu National High School who are at risk of dropping out.

Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What are the reasons among students who are at-risk of dropping out?
2. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention could be developed?

METHODOLOGY

A qualitative research approach was employed in this study in which it described the reasons of dropped out students in dropping from school where the purposive sampling technique in choosing them was used. Purposive sampling refers to a group of

non-probability sampling techniques in which units are selected because they have characteristics that we need in our sample. In other words, units are selected “on purpose” in purposive sampling (Nikolopoulou, 2022).

Interview guide questions were utilized in dealing with an interview with the participants on their reasons of dropping out from school. As Patton (2015) confirmed that interview guides ensure that the same topics are covered in each interview, facilitating comparability of responses. Also, Rubin and Rubin (2012) noted that it helps researchers dig deeper into topics by outlining probing questions. This encourages interviewees to provide more detailed and thoughtful responses. This consistency is essential in multi-person studies to maintain the reliability and validity of the data.

In this study, the researchers set the criteria on how to analyze and interpret the data. The researchers analyzed and interpreted the data gathered which served as the guide in formulating for a comprehensive program specifically on the establishment of a School-Based Teen Center in Lun Padidu National High School.

Thus, thematic analysis was utilized in analyzing the reasons of the participants who were at risk of dropping out.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. **Themes and Thematic Statements on the Experiences of the Learners at risk in dropping out.**

Essential Themes	Thematic Statements
A. Lack of Interest	Majority of the participants have lack of interest.
B. Health Issues	Secondary to the reasons from the participants at risk of dropping out have health issues
C. Family- related issues	Some reasons of dropping out from the participants engaged in family related issues.
D. Distance from home to school	Least of reasons from participants fall on the far distance from home to school

A. Lack of Interest

During the document analysis and interview conducted, the researchers had found out that, majority of the participants have lack of interest in school. These are reflected in the statements appearing on the following page.

SP-1: I don't feel like going to school ma'am because I lack sleep from playing online games to much.

SP-2: I lost interest in going to school Ma'am because I'm afraid of being called upon by the teacher to read. I don't know how to read well, and my classmates might laugh at me.

B. Health Issues

Secondary to the reasons from the participants at risk of dropping out have health issues as they confirmed.

SP-1: I keep getting sick, Ma'am. The pain in my head keeps coming back.

SP-2: I frequently have toothaches, Ma'am, almost every day it hurts, so I can't go to school

C. Family- Related Issues

Some of the participants engaged in family related issues.

SP-1: Mama and Papa separated, Ma'am, and I wasn't supported by them.

SP-2: Mama and Papa separated, Ma'am, so I'm the one taking care of my siblings.

D. Distance from home to school

Some reasons of the participants fall on the far distance from home to school,

SP-1: Our house is very far from school Ma'am, and I have to cross a river.

SP-2: Our house, Ma'am, is very far from the school, and I have to walk to school because I don't have money for transportation.

Generally, majority of the participants who were at risk in dropping out have the following reasons: lack of interest in school, health issues, family related issues, and distance from home to school where Dynarski et al. (2008) noted that the behavioral issues, mental health challenges and peer influence to the dropout phenomenon. Also, Jimerson et al. (2000) noted that there are early socio-emotional and behavioral characteristics that distinguish which retained students are most likely to drop out of high school. In addition, maternal level of education and academic achievement in the secondary grades were also associated with high school graduation status.

Indeed, there is a need for the school administration to give attention on the status of these learners who were at risk of dropping out by establishing a School-Based Teen Center. For this reason, the researchers recommend that the school-based Teen Center should be established to address the needs of the learners who are at risk of dropping out.

Intervention Program

The establishment of a School-Based Teen Center will provide a holistic support system that addresses not only academic needs but also social, emotional, and mental health challenges by offering tutoring, mentoring, counseling, and extracurricular activities under one roof. It is confirmed by Mahoney, Stattin, and Lord (2004) that teen centers provide safe, supervised environments that reduce the likelihood of engaging in risky behaviors such as substance abuse, violence, and delinquency. By offering constructive activities, these centers channel the energy of adolescents into positive outlets. This project will create a comprehensive safety net for students grappling with various issues. Thus, this will complement and reinforce the role of schools, families, and communities in educating, counseling, and empowering the learners.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, lack of interest was the major reason why learners were at risk of dropping out.

Recommendations

1. The researchers recommend the full and immediate attention of personnel must be done-the establishment of the school-based Teen Center.
2. School-based Teen Center can continue to serve as a beacon of hope and support for at risk students, ultimately reducing dropout rates and empowering them to overcome obstacles and thrive academically and personally.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors had emphasized to the participants that they don't have conflicts of interest regarding the research, authorship, and/or publication of this endeavor. The authors were accomplished this study in compliance with the research ethics protocol. Informed consent was given to each participant before the conduct of the study. The data were treated with utmost confidentiality.

Acknowledgements

The researchers were very thankful for the following who contributed to the success of this endeavor. First, to almighty God who bestowed them knowledge and perseverance in pursuing this study, all praises unto him. Second, to the school principal of Lun Padidu National high School, Susana S. Sumagka for giving them an opportunity to present this undertaking. Lastly, to the respondents who untiringly responded during the data gathering. From the bottom of their hearts, the researchers gave their great gratitude for the good deeds they contributed.

REFERENCES

- Adams, D. (2019). *Adolescent development and school support systems*. New York: Educational Psychology Press.
- Dynarski, SM. (2008). The lengthening of childhood. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, American Economic Association, vol. 22(3), pages 71-92, Summer.
- Jimerson, S. (2014). Exploring the association between grade retention and dropout: A longitudinal study examining socio-emotional, behavioral, and achievement characteristics of retained students. *The California Psychologist* (7) 1. DOI: 10.1007/BF03340889
- Jones, S. (2021). *Promoting positive youth development through after-school programs*. Chicago: Youth Services Journal.
- Mahoney, J. L., Stattin, H., & Lord, H. (2004). Unstructured youth recreation and antisocial behavior. *Journal of Adolescence*, 27(6), 527-540.
- Nikolopoulou, K. (2022). Probability sampling: Types & examples. Scribbr. Available at: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/probability-sampling/>​contentReference[oaicite:0]{index=0}.
- Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice*. Sage.
- Roberts, L. & Walker, K. (2020). The role of teen centers in supporting adolescent mental health. *Journal of School Counseling*, 14(2), 45-57.
- Rubin, H. J., & Rubin, I. S. (2012). *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data*. Sage Publications.
- Rumberger, R. W., & Rotermund, S. (2012). *The relationship between engagement and high school dropout*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.